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NATURE AND CONTENT OF EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES

Abstract.

The history of training technology began in the second half of the 20th century with the creation of technical devices for testing knowledge. For a while, training was understood as the use of technical means in technological training. Scientists believe that the use of technology is helpful to provide more information. But the inclusion of technology in the educational process is actively developing at different stages of the educational process. Scientists predict that in the future there will be independent use of educational (training) systems without the help of teachers and schools. Starting from the 50s of the 20th century, the search of scientists went in a different direction. As a result, not only teaching techniques, but also technological concepts enter the scientific circulation. Programmed training, then informatics, cybernetics and systems approach became a basis for understanding the learning process as technology.

Keywords: computer, technology, software, programmed, technique, pedagogy, elementary, process, training.

Pedagogy is a new look at the technological learning process. According to this view, the training process should be a maximally controlled process, unlike traditional training. The history of training technology began with the creation of technical devices for testing knowledge in the second half of the 20th century. For a while, training was understood as the use of technical means in technological training. Scientists believe that the use of technology is helpful to provide more information. But the inclusion of technology in the educational process is actively developing at different stages of the educational process. Scientists predict that in the future there will be independent use of educational (training) systems without the help of teachers and schools. Starting from the 50s of the 20th century, the search of scientists went in a different direction. As a result, not only teaching techniques, but also technological concepts enter the scientific circulation. Programmed training, then informatics, cybernetics and systems approach became a basis for understanding the learning process as technology. They began to look at the training process as a wide system. This included everything from goals to monitoring results. Education has always been the focus of people's attention since the beginning of human society. It is known that there was no school, no education system during the primitive community structure. People gathered together in certain caves, engaged in hunting and tried to meet their needs.

In the slavery system, men were engaged in the education of boys, and women were engaged in the education of girls. The men taught the boys how to hunt, while the girls were busy doing their own chores in the cave. However, education appeared later because it is related to literacy and writing. The first cultural revolution in the history of the development of civilization occurred with the appearance of writing. Because after the emergence of writing, literacy education was born. The teachers started to teach the students. As life develops, science, education and literacy also begin to develop.

The network of schools is expanding. Secular sciences and religious sciences were taught in these schools. Great successes and achievements were achieved in the field of training and education in ancient India, Jin, Greece, and Rome. In ancient Rome and Greece, great philosophers such as Socrates, Aristotle and Plato appeared as the most prominent scientists of their time. Zoroastrianism began to operate in Azerbaijan. Zoroaster, who lived and created in the 6th century BC, as an Azerbaijani, gave his famous work "Avesta" to the treasure of world culture. A very small part of this work, written on the skin of a thousand oxen, has come down to us. In "Avesta" a lot of space has been given to educational issues. Here, attachment to the land, loving the land, being addicted to hard work, respecting and caring for elders, children, the elderly, fathers and mothers, always being ready to protect the homeland, etc. such high moral and ethical standards are reflected. Zarathustra, who had great respect for science, education, and teachers, paid special attention to the interpretation and explanation of these issues in his work "Avesta". In all centuries of our era, education, training, evolution and development of the teacher were considered the main means. An educator-teacher is a teacher, and a student is a learner. In this sense, a good teacher should be a symbol of ideality for students. There should be a real example for them. After the union with Russia, there was an endless interest in Russian culture, Russian literature, and Russian science. Many Azerbaijani children who continued their education in Russia had the opportunity to acquire world culture and study its achievements through the Russian language.

In the 19th century, in a number of regions of Azerbaijan, Russian-language emergency schools were opened in Sheki, Shamakhi, Ganja, Nakhchivan, Baku, and Lankaran, and specialist teachers began to teach in those schools. In the 19th century, the actualization of education models was already underway. It began to be felt that education was put in the forefront of preparing people for professional activity and life. Tsarist Russia

needed officials who knew the Azerbaijani language. Accordingly, in Baku, Shamakhi, Sheki, Lankaran, Ganja and other large residential and industrial centers of Azerbaijan, Russian language schools were opened along with Azerbaijani language. For example, the famous writer and dramatist M.F. Akhundov studied at the Russian-Tatar school opened in Sheki in the 1830s. The famous writer, poet, philosopher Bakikhanov studied at the same type of school opened in Baku. Later, both geniuses served in the tsarist army and rose to the rank of colonel. The opening of schools played a great role in the education of the people. Each country has its own education system, education policy, education and development concept. During the 70 years of the USSR, the administrative emirate method prevailed. In other words, schools were managed by orders from above. The independent government of Azerbaijan, which is dominated by democracy and pluralism, has its own education and educational concept. In connection with the reconstruction of schools, the Law on Education of the Republic of Azerbaijan and Reform Programs on Education were adopted. In accordance with the requirements of both the Law on Education and the Reform programs on education, the following tasks have been set before the Pedagogical community of the Republic:

1. To ensure the comprehensive and harmonious development of the new human personality;
2. To reveal the regularities of personality formation;
3. Generalize and disseminate advanced pedagogical experience;
4. Develop the teacher's educational activities based on theoretical methodology;
5. To organize the training of the young generation.

Collaborative (collective) learning technology - the main idea in this learning technology is not to do something together, but to learn together. The technology of collective learning was developed by Ravin and his students, pedagogues from the USA and Israel, from the 80s of XX. This collective mutual learning technology has the following advantages:

- 1) As a result of regularly repeated exercises, students' logical thinking and understanding habits improve;
- 2) In the process of oral speech and during the discussion of the work done, students' intellectual activity habits develop, and their previously gained experience and knowledge become relevant;
- 3) Each child working in groups feels free and performs training tasks at his own pace;
- 4) The child is responsible for the result of both his own work and the work of the team;
- 5) The child develops the ability to evaluate his personal qualities, opportunities and abilities;
- 6) Discussion of this information with different partners increases the amount of associative connection. Thus, appropriation is further strengthened.

In this method, the core members of the group work on the topic in conjunction with their peers. Together they try to achieve the set goal. The tasks and the time allotted for their completion are different. Teams

do not compete with each other, they prepare answers to different tasks in different periods of time. The success of any group depends on the individual responsibility and diligence of its members. Therefore, all members of the group try to master the given task and materials well. When working with the collective, the main task of the teacher is not to blame the children for not knowing and not being able to announce them in the class, but to guide them to learn what they do not know and what they are not able to do. During their activity, the teacher should monitor the work done by the children, and if necessary, help the group in need. The teacher should help in a kind, calm manner and convey this to the children who are having a group discussion. If the group cannot cope with the given task, there are 2 reasons for this:

- I. the task is too difficult and complex;
Children have not developed strong practical habits to achieve
- II. task. In all these cases, work should be done in the direction of increasing the teacher's pedagogical skills.

Learning technology with the project method - The project method was developed in the USA by John Dewey and his student Kill Patrin in the 20s of the 20th century. With this method, active learning is structured according to the student's personal interests with appropriate activities. The main essence of the method is to show that the knowledge acquired by children is necessary for them in life. In the educational process, the student is taught to use the knowledge he has and will acquire to solve the most important problem taken from real life, which is unfamiliar to him, important for him. The teacher can show the source of obtaining new information and tell how to search for this information, can direct the child. From the projects method children are directed to perform independent activity for a certain period of time individually, in pairs and in groups, always to solve some problem. In addition to applying various training methods and tools in solving the problem, it is also intended to interactively use tested knowledge in various fields of science and technology. The project method as the basis of modern pedagogical technologies - from various training tools and information technologies is realized by using Both modern (computer telecommunications, electronic databases, video and multimedia tools, fax, video communication) and traditional (science and information books, video recordings, etc.) can be used as teaching aids. Also, the project method is performed on a complex problem.

Module training technology – Realization of the personality-oriented concept in training, designing and practical application of developmental pedagogical technologies requires testing them in different conditions, on different topics, and studying pedagogical experience in this field. A new pedagogy that has been shown wide interest in its application in schools one of the technologies is module training technology. By modular technology of training, it is understood that children independently achieve specific learning goals in the modular work process in class and outside of class. A. Mehrabov, A. Agayev, H. Ahmadov, A. Abbasov, Z. Zeynalov, R. Hasanov, F. Rustamov, M.

Ilyasov and others are prominent research scientists. they divide the structure of the technological approach into two parts, vertical and horizontal. In the vertical structure of such a technological approach, it is necessary to distinguish interrelated meta-, macro-, meso- and micro-technologies. Mathematical technology is a general pedagogical (general didactic, general education) technology that allows implementing social policy in the field of education at the social and pedagogical level. Macrotechnology or technology in the fields of education covers a certain direction of the educational process of any field of study, fields of activity related to the teaching of the subject at the general pedagogical and general methodical level. Mesotechnology or local modular technology is a technology applied to solve issues related to separate parts (modules) of the educational process, special, didactic, methodical or a certain problem area of education. Microtechnology is a tech-

nology related to the solution of operational issues, mutual relations, and writing habits between the subjects of the pedagogical process. Examples of such technologies are technologies related to the formation of writing habits, the organization of trainings for the correction of personal qualities of the subject (personality, participants of the educational process). (See: A. Mehrabov, A. Abbasov, Z. Zeynalov, R. Hasanov. Pedagogical technologies. Baku-2006, p. 11)

Reference list:

1. Agayev A. Learning process: Tradition and modernity. Baku, 2006.
2. Garalov Z. Education (principles, content, methodology), I, II, III volumes. Baku, 2003.
3. Nazarov A., Mammadov R. Pedagogical mastery. Teaching materials. Baku, 2008.
4. Nazarov A., Mollayeva E. Educational problems of the modern era. Textbook. Baku, 2011.